

Synthesis of 4,4'-Bithiazoles and 4-(2-Thiazolyl)-aminoquinolines and Their Antiamoebic Activities

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4,4'-Bithiazoles and 4-(2-thiazolyl)-aminoquinolines having substitutions in thiazole and quinoline moieties have been synthesized. All these compounds have shown good *in vitro* antiamoebic activity.

SULFUR containing compounds are particularly known for their effectiveness against bacteria. Thiazolidine and thiazole compounds possess fungicidal and other biological properties¹. 2-Amino-5-nitro-thiazole nucleus possesses broad profile of antiparasitic activities like schistosomiasis, histomoniasis and amoebiasis². 2-Acetamido-5-nitro-thiazole have been reported to be effective against *Trypanosoma cruzi* in mice³. 8-Hydroxyquinoline derivatives and 4-substituted-7-chloroquinolines have been extensively used as powerful antiamoebic drugs⁴⁻⁶. It is expected that the introduction of thiazole moiety in the quinoline and hydroxyquinoline moieties would modulate the biological activity of the compounds. The drugs, having pharmacophores against *E. histolytica* and bacteria are expected to be highly effective against bacterial infections as well as against amoebiasis. It is particularly important as it is well known that enteric bacteria are involved in the pathogenesis of amoebiasis⁷.

We report in this communication the synthesis and antiamoebic activity of 4-substituted amino-thiazolyl-7-chloroquinoline, 4-substituted aminothiazolyl-8-hydroxyquinoline derivatives and a few bithiazole derivatives.

The synthesis of 2,2'-diamino-(4,4')bithiazole has been reported⁸. The compound was nitrated or acetylated and then nitrated to obtain 2,2'-diamino-5,5'-dinitro-(4,4')-bithiazole and 2,2'-diacetylamino-(4,4')-bithiazole and 2,2'-diacetylamino-5,5'-dinitro-(4,4')-bithiazole (I).

4,7-Dichloroquinoline, 2-methyl-4-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline or 2-methyl-3-*n*-propyl-4-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline was condensed with 2-amino-thiazole derivative following method (a) or (b) to produce the corresponding 4-substituted quinoline (II).

Biological activity :

In vitro testing of the drugs :

LD-strains of *E. histolytica* with a mixed bacterial flora were used as the test organism. Goat serum

was prepared and inactivated in the way described previously⁹. The stock cultures of *E. histolytica* were grown in a modification of Boeck and Drbohlav medium¹⁰ containing egg slant and goat serum supplemented with a loopful of rice starch. The medium was buffered with *M*/40 sodium hydrogen phosphate and the pH ranged from 7.0 to 7.4. The temperature was maintained at 37°.

The technique of cultivation of *E. histolytica* was the same as reported earlier⁹ and we followed essentially the same method as used by Dutta *et al*^{11,12} and Kausiva and Pujari⁷ for drug testing.

All the drugs tested are highly insoluble in water but considerably soluble in acid or alkali. The compounds were soluble in DMSO but dilution with normal saline caused immediate precipitation of the drugs. No attempt was made to make the drugs soluble. Fine suspensions of the drugs were made in normal saline and successive two-fold serial dilutions were obtained.

Generally, 4 day old cultures were examined under an inverted microscope (10X ocular and 20X objective) and the tubes showing 20-25 × 10⁴ amoebae/ml were used as seed for drug testing. 0.2 ml of this amoebic suspension was used for inoculation. 1 ml of the drug suspension in normal saline was added to 9 ml (containing 8.8 ml of medium + 0.2 ml of inoculum) in each culture tube

TABLE 1—CHARACTERIZATION DATA ON SUBSTITUTED 2,2'-DIAMINO-(4,4')BITHIAZOLE AND OTHER KNOWN COMPOUNDS AND THEIR *in vitro* AMOEBICIDAL END POINTS

Compound	m.p. °C	yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			Minimal inhibitory conc. (g/ml)
				C	H	N	
*1. 2-Amino-5-nitrothiazole							31.3
2. 2,2'-Diamino-5,5'-dinitro-(4,4')bithiazole	did not melt at 350	35	C ₈ H ₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	24.80 (25.00)	1.15 (1.38)	28.80 (29.16)	125.0
3. 2,2'-Diacetylamino-(4,4')bithiazole	did not melt at 350	40	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	42.32 (42.55)	3.40 (3.54)	19.65 (19.85)	15.6
4. 2,2'-Diacetylamino-5,5'-dinitro-(4,4')-bithiazole	did not melt at 350	35	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	31.92 (32.26)	1.95 (2.15)	22.38 (22.58)	62.5
*5. 4-(2-Thiazolyl)amino-† 7-chloroquinoline	190-92	30	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ SCl	54.7 (55.08)	2.85 (3.06)	15.8 (16.06)	62.5
6. 4-(5-Nitro-2-thiazolyl)- amino-7-chloroquinoline	200-02	25	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	46.6 (46.99)	1.9 (2.28)	17.9 (18.27)	125.0
7. 4-(2-Thiazolyl)amino-2- methyl-8-hydroxyquinoline	183-84	25	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS	60.5 (60.71)	3.90 (4.28)	16.1 (16.34)	62.5
8. 4-(5-Nitro-2-thiazolyl)- amino-2-methyl-8- hydroxyquinoline	198-200	20	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	51.45 (51.65)	3.05 (3.31)	18.2 (18.54)	62.5
9. 4-(5-Nitro-2-thiazolyl)- amino-2-methyl-8- methoxyquinoline	180-82	20	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	52.9 (53.16)	3.6 (3.79)	17.5 (17.72)	31.3
10. 4-(5-Nitro-2-thiazolyl)- amino-2-methyl-3- <i>n</i> -propyl- 8-methoxyquinoline	200-92	25	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	56.9 (56.98)	4.9 (5.03)	15.45 (15.64)	15.6
*11. Emetine hydrochloride							7.8
*12. Metronidazole							7.8
*13. 7-Iodo-5-chloro- 8-hydroxyquinoline							62.5

* Known compounds ; * Lit.¹² m.p. 231-233 ; † M.S. gave $\frac{m}{e}$ 261.

Preparation method : (a) 5, 7, 8 and 10.
(b) 6 and 9.

in duplicate to give a drug concentration of 1000 µg/ml. Eight successive two-fold serial dilutions of the drug in normal saline were made and the drugs were added in the same way as before in subsequent duplicate tubes. Strict aseptic conditions were maintained. Drug dilutions were sterilized by autoclaving at 10 lb/sq inch for 15 min before test. The tests were run for 48 hr and incubation were carried out at 37°. The cultures were examined after 48 hr for viable and motile amoeba. The results were further confirmed by sub-culture.

The operations were repeated to examine the reproducibility of the results. The minimum inhibitory concentration (M.I.C.) values of some drugs are also included for comparison. No attempt has been made to study the selective inhibitory effect of bacterial associates which probably influence end point activity.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded in nujol on a Perkin Elmer 237 grating spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined in capillary tubes using Gallenkamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected.

The general methods followed for the synthesis of 4-substituted quinolines are :

Method (a) : A mixture of 4-chloroquinoline derivative (0.005 mole) and 2-amino thiazole derivative (0.005 mole) was refluxed with phenol (5 ml) in an oil bath for 24 hr. The mass was then acidified with dil. HCl, phenol was extracted out with ether, the aqueous acid layer was basified with NH₃ and the material was filtered. It was crystallized from alcohol

Method (b) : The method was almost the same as in (a) but phenol was replaced by xylene (20 ml) and pyridine (0.5 ml).

Other compounds were prepared as follows :

2,2'-Diamino-5,5'-dinitro-(4,4')-bithiazole : 2,2'-Diamino-(4,4')-bithiazole was prepared by the literature method⁸. The compound (1.20 g) was dissolved in conc. H₂SO₄ (5 ml) and cooled to 10°. Fuming HNO₃ (1 ml) was added to it with cooling and the mixture left overnight. The mass was then poured into ice-water, the nitrated product was filtered out and crystallized from dil. alcohol. IR (nujol) : 3450, 3300 (NH) cm⁻¹.

2,2'-Diacetylamino-(4,4')-bithiazole : The compound was prepared by acetylation of the corresponding amine with acetic anhydride and crystallized

from alcohol. IR (nujol) : 3450 (NH), 1640 (C=O) cm^{-1} .

2,2'-Diacetyl-amino-5,5'-dinitro-(4,4')-bithiazole : 2,2'-Diacetyl amino-(4,4')-bithiazole (0.5 g) was dissolved in conc. H_2SO_4 (4 ml) cooled at 10° . It was then nitrated with fuming nitric acid (0.2 ml), left overnight and poured into ice-water. The product was filtered out and crystallized from dilute alcohol. IR (nujol) : 3460 (NH), 1650 (C=O) cm^{-1} . Characterization data and *in vitro* amoebicidal activities of the compounds are recorded in Table 1.

Discussion

The 2-amino-5-nitro thiazole is known to be effective against bacterial infections. The effectiveness of 2-amino-5-nitro thiazole and 8-hydroxyquinolines as anti-amoebic agents are known. Thus, the compounds having 2-amino-5-nitro thiazole and 8-hydroxy or alkoxy quinoline moieties are expected to have enhanced anti-amoebic activity which have been corroborated from *in vitro* testing. It has been found that molecular doubling sometimes leads to enhanced drug activities. This has been found to be true for 2,2'-diacetyl-amino-4,4'-thiazole but the introduction of $-\text{NO}_2$ group in 5,5'-positions have been found to have adverse effects on drug activities.

The drug activities of 8-hydroxyquinoline are believed to be due to chelation with ferrous ion necessary for the growth of amoeba though killing amoeba by inhibition of the supporting micro organisms or by direct action has also been reported¹⁴. The effectiveness of chelation is also confirmed from the comparison of 8-hydroxy (or alkoxy) which is likely to be hydrolyzed to hydroxy quinolines (7-10) and quinolines (5-6). The presence of CH_3 or Pr groups in 2 or 3 positions is likely to increase the electron densities of N-atoms thereby increasing the

acid dissociation constants and chelating capabilities of the ligands probably leading to enhanced amoebicidal activities of compounds No. 9 and 10. However, the activities of these compounds are likely to be due to bactericidal effects of sulphur compounds which act indirectly by inhibition of the supporting intestinal bacterial flora necessary for the survival of amoeba.

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References

1. A. R. SURREY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3354.
2. A. C. CUCKLER, A. B. KUFFERBERG and N. MILLMAN, *Antibiot. Chemotherapy*, 1955, **5**, 540.
3. F. HAWKING in "Experimental Chemotherapy", (Ed.), R. J. SCHNITZER and F. HAWKING, Academic Press, Inc., New York, N. Y., 1963, Vol. 1, p. 205.
4. D. V. DUTTA, S. A. K. SINGH and P. M. CHUTLANI, *Amer. Jour. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1974, **23**, 586.
5. S. P. BENNETT and D. A. FRANCO, *J. Amer. Med. Ass.*, 1969, **154**, 58.
6. P. E. THOMPSON and J. W. REINERTSON, *Amer. J. Trop. Med.*, 1951, **31**, 707.
7. B. S. KAUSIVA and H. K. PUJARI, *Jour. Sci. Indust. Res.*, 1956, **15C**, 160.
8. H. ERLENMEYER and K. MENZI, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1948, **31**, 2065.
9. S. DUTTA, A. PAL, B. P. DRY and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 902.
10. C. DOBELL and P. P. LAIDLAW, *Parasitology*, 1926, **18**, 283.
11. G. P. DUTTA, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1966, **6**, 88.
12. J. N. S. YADAVA and G. P. DUTTA, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1973, **61**, 971.
13. K. GANAPATHI and M. H. SHAH, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1951, **34A**, 178.
14. P. E. THOMPSON, J. W. REINERTSON, A. BAYLES, D. A. MCCARTHY and E. F. ELSLAGER, *Amer. J. Trop. Med. Hgg.*, 1955, **4**, 224.